

Impact of Consumers' Brand Loyalty Towards Nestlé Products in NCR, India

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess customers' loyalty to global brands by examining the factors influencing brand loyalty. Consumers assess products based on intrinsic and extrinsic cues, and various factors contribute to their loyalty. The research focused on revealing the relationship between brand loyalty and its determinants, specifically emphasizing the brand's name, design, quality, price, and promotion. The primary objectives were to investigate the factors impacting brand loyalty for Nestlé products, identify the most influential factors in Nestlé product loyalty, and assess the correlation between consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty for Nestlé products. The research employed a descriptive survey research design, utilizing a structured questionnaire for data collection. The data analysis was conducted using Partial Least Squares (PLS). The study was carried out in the North and Central Region (NCR) of India, with a sample size of 225 participants. The findings indicate that the key factors influencing consumer brand loyalty are the brand's name, quality, price, and promotion.

Keywords: brand name, product quality, price, design, promotion, and brand loyalty.

1. Introduction

Nestlé is the world's leading company dedicated to health, nutrition, and wellness, with its headquarters situated in Vevey, Switzerland. Renowned for its exceptional products, Nestlé has earned unmatched trust in the food industry. The company offers a wide array of products, ranging from baby food, bottled water, chocolate, and coffee to dairy products, healthcare, and sports nutrition. Since its founding, Nestlé has prioritized nutrition as the cornerstone of its business. Nestlé India Limited operates as an international sub-brand of Swiss-based Nestlé, headquartered in Gurugram, Haryana. The company's offerings include a range of products, including food, beverages, chocolates, and confectionery. Emphasizing its commitment to quality, Nestlé's slogan resonates with "Good Food, Good Life".

The establishment of Nestlé's first factory in Punjab in 1961 was a response to the Indian government's desire for Nestlé to contribute to the development of the dairy economy. Nestlé aligns itself with the aspirations of India, contributing significantly to employment opportunities for ten million individuals, encompassing farmers, packaging material suppliers, service providers, and other suppliers. Nestlé India has established a solid reputation by offering customers a varied selection of high-quality health products at accessible prices. The extent of customer loyalty to Nestlé products has been discussed using five elements: brand name, quality, price, design, and promotion. All international companies enter international markets in order to increase their profits and market share. Therefore, there is a relationship between consumer loyalty to the brand and increased demand for goods bearing this brand, which positively affects the company's profitability and market share.

Despite the fact that brand loyalty among consumers affects a company's profitability and market share, there has been little and conflicting research on consumer loyalty. In recent years, the subject of customer loyalty has generated a great deal of debate among academics and business professionals. In this study, brand loyalty of The Nestlé brand is examined. To understand the developments' impact on consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty, it is further intended to examine the development of global brand and consumer loyalty. Therefore, determining the Effect of a global brand on consumer

loyalty is the aim of the research. The study is limited to the NCR region of India. The study is limited to the variables of brand name, product quality, price, design, promotion, and brand loyalty.

2. Literature review

Brand loyalty

Research suggests a positive and significant correlation between brand awareness and brand image. Moreover, there exists a noteworthy connection between brand image and brand loyalty in the context of brand equity, where brand awareness serves as a mediator for both brand image and brand equity associations (Zia et al., 2021). In addition, studies indicate that tourism organizations express positive intentions to employ gamification as a strategy to elevate customer engagement, brand awareness, and loyalty toward tourism sites (Abou-Shouk et al., 2021).

According to Rehman and Akhtar (2012), brand loyalty exhibited by a customer goes beyond mere repurchasing; it encompasses a psychological commitment to the brand. This implies that customers, demonstrating brand loyalty, not only make frequent purchases of the brand but also exhibit a reluctance to buy any other brand, even if the alternative brand is of equal or superior quality. Another study demonstrated that brand loyalty is distinguished by a steadfast and enduring commitment to repeatedly choose the favored product or service in the future. This commitment entails consistently opting for the same brand or a set of brands, irrespective of situational influences and marketing initiatives, and possesses the capability to discourage switching behavior (Oliver, 1997).

All of the causal factors were found to have a favorable effect on brand loyalty for Thai canned tuna. Furthermore, brand attitudes, brand quality, and brand value were ranked second and third as affecting brand loyalty. (Chuenban, et al.,2021). Delgado et al (2001) study showed that brand loyalty has a big influence on a customer's purchasing decision and prevents them from switching to a competitor's brand. (Delgado et al.,2001).

Another investigation highlighted that maintaining current customers is more economical than acquiring new ones. Consequently, fostering customer loyalty is essential for minimizing the costs linked to acquiring new customers (Rowley, 2005). In addition, other research has explored the dual influence of brand loyalty on product quality, both positive and negative, and examined its direct and indirect effects on brand loyalty (Aaker, 2003). Aaker (1990) also points out that various factors, including user experience, influence customer loyalty. High switching barriers arising from technological, economic, or psychological factors can contribute to customer loyalty by making switching to alternative options costly or difficult.

Brand's Name

A brand, as per Keller (2003), refers to a name, symbol, design, or a combination thereof that sets a product apart from its competitors. Keller emphasizes that a memorable name and a positive image alone are insufficient; instead, he asserts that an organization should impart knowledge. Hasan (2008) proposes two approaches to handling a brand. The first involves viewing the brand as a descriptor, providing consumers with awareness through names and logos. Alternatively, considering the brand as an experiential provider entails recognizing the sensory, emotional, creative, and lifestyle connections associated with the name and logo for other customers and consumers. A study by Witek (2022) Showed that not every brand name from a foreign-developed country may contribute to a rise in purchase intentions. Brand name in an emerging market may result in lower purchasing intentions.

Brand identity has an impact on brand performance, according to research. In addition, there was a link found between brand identity and brand satisfaction. Other evidence suggests that brand identity has an impact on brand love. (Souri,2021). In the year 2021, Cuong et al. identified that brand awareness has a favorable impact on both brand image and loyalty. Furthermore, their results demonstrated a positive influence of brand image on brand loyalty. Additionally, the study uncovered that brand image played a moderating role in the connection between brand awareness and brand loyalty. These conclusions emphasize the significance of branding in the context of SME internationalization, as highlighted by Jin et al. in 2018. A study showed that brand affection is influenced by factors such as social identity, brand image, and consumer satisfaction (Al-Haddad, 2019). Another study suggested that early-acquired phonemes are more effective for every day-use brand, whereas late-acquired phonemes are more suitable for luxury goods (Pathak et al., 2017). The results also indicated that logos featuring both an icon and a brand name are perceived as more attractive than logos with only one element, and black logos are considered more appealing than colored logos (Bresciani et al., 2017).

Two separate studies were conducted. In the first study, it was observed that brand names featuring higher-frequency sounds are more effective in conveying ethical qualities compared to those with lower-frequency sounds. The second study revealed that when additional information, particularly information reflecting negatively on the brand's ethical conduct, is present, brand names can positively influence Customer-Perceived Ethicality (CPE) (Klink et al., 2017). Another investigation demonstrated that, in terms of relationship quality, brand logo benefit predicts all three variables,

whereas brand logo identification only predicts satisfaction and trust. Brand logo benefit emerges as a more robust predictor of satisfaction, trust, and commitment than the other two variables (Japutra et al., 2015).

Product Quality

Product quality exerts a positive and noteworthy influence on brand image, trust, and customer satisfaction, with brand image and brand trust similarly contributing positively and significantly to satisfaction (Diputra et al., 2021). Assessing inventory performance through metrics such as inventory efficiency, inventory productivity, and inventory vulnerability reveals a favorable impact of inventory performance on product quality (Lin et al., 2018). Anam et al.'s (2018) investigation suggests that products labeled as halal create a psychological impression related to the quality of the food product. Additionally, the study by Wiharso et al. (2022) demonstrated a positive and significant correlation between product quality and customer satisfaction, as well as a positive and significant effect of promotion on customer satisfaction. Furthermore, Syafarudin's (2021) study indicated an association between product quality, customer quality, and loyalty, highlighting that product quality influences customer quality, which in turn affects customer loyalty.

A study by Hakim (2021) linked product quality to customer satisfaction and loyalty, establishing a positive and significant influence of product quality on both customer satisfaction and loyalty. According to Rivai (2021), product quality and price perception play a significant role in consumer happiness, with no similar impact observed for purchase decisions. However, another study by Tjahjono et al. (2021) identified a positive and substantial association between product quality and brand image factors in influencing purchase decisions, indicating that customers base their purchase decisions on these aspects. Furthermore, customer satisfaction is positively affected by purchase decisions, with product quality playing a significant and positive role in influencing customer satisfaction. In a separate study, Fathurahman et al. (2022) unveiled that the combined influence of product quality, promotion, and brand image significantly contributes to customer satisfaction. Moreover, although promotion negatively impacts repurchase interest, both brand image and product quality exhibit positive and significant effects on repurchase interest. The study conducted by Zhao et al. (2021) found that ensuring product quality and food safety emerges as an effective strategy for agro-food processing enterprises to improve their financial performance.

In the era of a globalized world and increasing market competition, providing a product of high quality can confer a competitive advantage to a company (Russell et al., 2006). The decision to purchase private labels is often closely linked to considerations of quality. Additionally, if a brand is perceived by consumers as high-quality, it enhances the likelihood of consumers choosing that brand due to the positive quality image associated with it (Uggla, 2001). To meet the expectations of the target consumer, the brand's material, color, and functionality should align with their demands (Frings, G. S., 2005). Given that product quality stands out as one of the pivotal factors influencing consumer purchases, various quality labels have been introduced to guarantee the quality and authenticity of products. This facilitates buyers in promptly recognizing high-quality products, enabling them to make more informed and discerning purchasing decisions (Košičiarová et al., 2016)

Price

Many studies have been conducted to explore the relationship between price and quality. A particular study underscored that price exerts a noteworthy and positive influence on both customer satisfaction and loyalty, with customer satisfaction subsequently playing a significant role in influencing customer loyalty (Wantara, 2019). Herman's findings indicate that perceptions of price directly influence satisfaction ratings and also indirectly influence satisfaction through perceptions of pricing fairness (Herrmann, 2007). Čater's (2009) research indicates that while price has a negative impact on satisfaction, factors such as delivery performance, supplier experience, and human interaction have positive effects. The study further reveals that price has a negative impact on behavioral loyalty, while product quality has a positive impact. In a study by Lim (2021), it was shown that price, transportation, and product quality contribute significantly to positive emotions in customers.

Another study conducted by Prasetyo et al. (2022) revealed that customer satisfaction is influenced by the combined effects of price, product quality, and service quality. Notably, product quality, price perception, and service quality were identified as factors exerting a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. In Dewi's (2022) study, it was concluded that both price and service quality contribute positively and significantly to consumer satisfaction, along with the positive effects of service quality, customer value, and price.

The data implies a robust connection between perceived fairness in pricing and both consumer satisfaction and loyalty. Furthermore, the results suggest that perceived service quality and equitable pricing jointly exert an indirect impact on customer loyalty through the mediating factor of consumer pleasure (Ahmed et al., 2022). In the context of the Celaket Batik Center in Malang City, it was observed that amenities and pricing significantly affect customer satisfaction, with pricing and amenities collectively contributing to customer satisfaction (Priambudi et al., 2022). A study focusing on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the food and beverage industry in Malaysia disclosed that price, promotion, place, and product all have positive effects on customer satisfaction (Sudari, 2019). Hatta et al.'s research

suggested that positive perceptions of product innovation, quality, price, promotion, and purchase decisions were observed among respondents. The study emphasized that product innovation and promotion had no impact on purchase decisions, whereas product quality and pricing influenced the decision-making process (Hatta et al., 2018).

Customers displaying strong brand loyalty are willing to pay a premium for their preferred brand, indicating that pricing has minimal influence on their purchase intentions (Cadogan et al., 2000). However, for the average consumer, pricing is a crucial factor, and individuals with strong brand loyalty are prepared to pay more for their favored brand, unaffected by pricing considerations in their buying decisions (Cadogan et al., 2000). Consumers who have a strong belief in the pricing and value of their preferred brands engage in price comparisons with competing companies (Keller, 2003). Furthermore, aligning pricing with perceived expenses and values can enhance customer satisfaction. Consumers are more likely to make a purchase if the perceived value of the product outweighs its cost. Loyal customers are willing to pay a higher price, even if the price has increased, as the perceived risk is significant, and they prefer paying more to avoid the risk of change (Yoon et al., 2000).

Design

Packaging emerges as a pivotal factor for any product, with characteristics such as color, packaging material, wrapper design, and innovation being particularly crucial criteria for consumers in their purchasing decisions, as noted by Raheem et al. (2014). Similarly, Waheed et al. (2018) found that product packaging significantly impacts consumer purchasing intent, with package material, packaging color, font style, packaging design, and printed content exerting the greatest influence on purchase intentions. Homburg et al. (2015) demonstrated that design dimensions positively affect willingness to pay and buying intention. The study by Zhang et al. (2021) revealed that concept innovativeness positively influences symbolic design perceptions, and innovativeness interacts with intensity to shape these views. Frings (2005) emphasized the impact of the visual appearance of a brand, including line, form, and details, on consumer perception. The form or shape of a product is identified as a critical factor influencing consumer interest and eventual purchase, making design a significant aspect of marketing activities that can differentiate a product from competitors, as highlighted by Kotler and Armstrong (2008).

Product design plays a crucial role in creating a brand image, and companies are increasingly recognizing the marketing value of product design, particularly its appearance, in customer purchasing decisions (1993) (Tsafarakis et al., 2011). Quality, an essential consideration in consumer purchasing decisions, is assessed through product design, encompassing all features that impact how the product is perceived, felt, and functions (Pihl, 2014). Mentioned that when creating a product, the corporation employs a variety of marketing strategies as well as a variety of design innovation strategies. (Sääksjärvi & Hellén 2013). Suggested that a market leader's design approach is vigorously implemented and consumer innovation has a favourable impact on design attitudes. (Perry & Kyriakaki, 2014).

Promotion

Promotion exerts a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction but has a simultaneously negative yet significant impact on repurchase interest, as outlined by Fathurahman and Sihite (2022). Another investigation conducted by Wibowo et al. (2021) showcased that promotion yields a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. The considerable impact of both price and sales promotion on customer satisfaction is also evident, as underscored in the research by Prasilowati et al. (2021). According to the findings from Kurniawan's study (2022), perceived sales promotion contributes positively to both customer satisfaction and loyalty. Additionally, the perceived benefits of booking apps and perceived sales promotion enhance customer satisfaction.

Contrastingly, Sanny et al.'s study (2021) reveals that, when compared to service, marketing has no apparent impact on consumer satisfaction. However, promotion has a substantial influence on repurchase intent, while service quality does not. This suggests that consumer satisfaction affects repurchase intent, whereas promotion influences repurchase intent through other variables.

Promotion is a vital element within a company's marketing strategy, as it serves as a means of communicating with customers to encourage the purchase or sale of products or services. Sales promotion tools are commonly used by most companies to complement their advertising and public relations initiatives, specifically targeting end users as consumers (Clow, 2010). Placed within the marketing mix, promotion includes various methods of communication with customers, including advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, and publicity. Advertising, which is characterized by the impersonal presentation of information through the media, significantly influences consumers' perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes toward products and brands and their ultimate purchasing decisions (Lovelock, 2010). In a broader context, promotion involves communicating with customers through advertising to persuade them to make a purchase. Meanwhile, service quality, which aims to meet customers' demands and requirements with the help of sales personnel, plays a crucial role in establishing healthy and long-term relationships with customers (Lau et al., 2006). From the above literature review the below hypothesis have been formulated:

H₀₁: brand 's name has no impact on brand loyalty.

H₀₂: product quality has no impact on brand loyalty.

H₀₃: price has no impact on brand loyalty.

H₀₄: design has no impact on brand loyalty.

H₀₅: promotion has no impact on brand loyalty.

Research Methodology:

For this research, a self-administered survey will be conducted through structured questionnaires on an internet-based platform. Following Sekaran and Bougie's (2011) recommendation, the use of questionnaires allows for reaching a diverse range of respondents, and the collected data can be readily analyzed. The questionnaire utilized in this study consists of three sections. Section A centers on the demographic information of respondents, whereas Section B delves into the independent variables such as brand name, quality, price, design, and promotion. Section C involves respondents answering questions related to consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty towards Nestlé products.

Section A of the survey comprises four straightforward questions related to age, marital status, income, and education level. The subsequent segments of the questionnaire utilize six-point Likert scales for measurement, ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The survey was conducted over a two-month period spanning from August to September 2022. In the demographic section of the questionnaire, information regarding respondents' age, marital status, highest education level, and income was examined. A total of 250 questionnaires were disseminated online through Google Forms, yielding 230 responses. However, only 225 responses were deemed usable due to incomplete answers from some respondents.

Table 1. Summary of Demographic Characteristics

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
16-24 years old	83	36.9
25-33 years old	107	47.6
34-45 years old	32	14.2
Above 42 years old	3	1.3
Marital status		
Married	69	30.7
Unmarried	156	69.3
Education level		
High School	4	1.8
Graduate	54	24.0
Postgraduate	124	55.1
Doctorate's degree	43	19.1
Monthly income		
5000- 15000	122	54.2
15001- 30000	46	20.4
More than 30000	47	20.9

Based on the result, a significant portion of the participants, comprising 47.6%, fell within the 25-33 age group. Following this, 36.9% of respondents were in the 16-24 age range, while the remaining 15.5% belonged to the age group above 33 years old. The demographic profile indicated that out of 225, 69.3% of them were unmarried, and the remaining 30.7% of the respondents were married. Additionally, most of the respondent's monthly income was between 5000-15000, which consisted of 54.2%. This was followed by 20.9%. Whose monthly income was more than 30000. This was followed by 20.4% who have a monthly income of 15001-30000.

4. Analysis and Discussion

• Reliability analysis

Data reliability was assessed, And Cronbach's alpha for all constructs ranged from 0.886 to 0.904. These values, exceeding the conventional threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2010), affirm the reliability of the constructs.

Table 2. Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Brand 's name	.895
Quality	.889
Price	.904
Design	.895
Promotion	.900
Behaviour	.886

- **Hypothesis Development through Regression analysis**

Regression was undertaken to find the impact of different variables on dependent variables of brand loyalty.

Table 3. summary of the hypothesis

Variables	Significant
Brand 's name	.000
Quality	.000
Price	.001
Design	.279
Promotion	.000

The significance value for the brand name was 0.000, indicating a significant relationship with consumer brand loyalty as the p-value was less than 0.05. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), significance values should be below 0.05 for acceptance. Therefore, the influence of the brand's name on consumer brand loyalty is statistically significant, and thus, H₀₁ is accepted.

Similarly, the significance value for quality was 0.000, demonstrating a significant relationship with consumer brand loyalty as the p-value was less than 0.05. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), significance values should be below 0.05 for acceptance. Therefore, the impact of quality on consumer brand loyalty is statistically significant, leading to the acceptance of H₀₂.

The significance value for the price variable was 0.001, indicating a significant relationship with consumer brand loyalty as the p-value was less than 0.05. As per Sekaran and Bougie (2010), significance values should be below 0.05 for acceptance. Thus, the Effect of price on consumer brand loyalty is statistically significant, and H₀₃ is accepted.

For the design variable, the significance value was 0.279, demonstrating a significant relationship with consumer brand loyalty as the p-value was less than 0.05. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), significance values should be below 0.05 for acceptance. Therefore, the impact of design on consumer brand loyalty is statistically significant, leading to the acceptance of H₀₄.

The significance value for the promotion variable was 0.000, indicating a significant relationship with consumer brand loyalty as the p-value was less than 0.05. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), significance values should be below 0.05 for acceptance. Hence, the impact of promotion on consumer brand loyalty is statistically significant, and H₀₅ is accepted.

Completion of the literature review and data analysis in this paper achieved the initial objective of the study, which was to “examine the factors influencing brand loyalty of Nestlé. Specific factors that influence brand loyalty for Nestlé include brand name, quality, price, and promotion. The second objective was met from the P value. Results displayed in the table clearly showed these brand's name, quality, and promotion were the factors that had the strongest significance on consumer brand loyalty as the significance they were at 0.000; these are the highest among all of the other factors than the price, which had 0.001, that had an impact on brand loyalty towards Nestlé brand. However, the design showed no impact on brand loyalty of the Nestlé brand, which has 0.297.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this investigation was to examine how participants are influenced by factors that contribute to brand loyalty, especially for the Nestlé brand. Brand loyalty holds great importance for organizations in ensuring that their products remain prominent in the minds of consumers and prevent them from switching to other brands. The research highlights the challenge of securing consumer loyalty and retention due to various factors, including competition and consumers' desire for variety.

The results of the study confirm the significant impact of the brand name, quality, and promotion in enhancing brand loyalty among consumers. Moreover, the overall results indicate that, among various factors, consumers mostly value price as a determinant of brand loyalty. These factors show positive relationships with brand loyalty, with the exception of design, which shows a negative relationship. However, consumer brand loyalty also shows a moderating effect on brand loyalty.

6. Recommendation

The results of the study confirm the existence of statistically significant positive correlations between brand loyalty and brand name, quality, price, and promotion. However, the study also reveals significant negative associations between brand loyalty and design. Based on these results, several recommendations can be proposed to formulate strategies to enhance brand loyalty among consumers. Of the five variables considered, namely brand name, quality, price, and promotion, they had the greatest influence on the consumer's decision-making process. This underscores the importance of companies constantly updating and improving their brand name, quality, price, and promotion to maintain a competitive position among competing companies. In addition, it is essential for companies to focus on innovation and improving their product design, as dissatisfaction with product design emerged as a major factor affecting consumer brand loyalty in this study.

The results indicate that consumers express satisfaction with the brand name, quality, price, and promotion of Nestlé products, which contributes positively to enhancing brand loyalty. However, dissatisfaction with the design of Nestlé products may lead to a potential shift in customer loyalty away from Nestlé products.

7. Limitation

One significant limitation of this study is its restricted geographical scope, focusing solely on one city in India, which may not be indicative of the entire population of the country. Consequently, the precision of the results in reflecting consumer intentions at a national level is compromised. Additionally, the study relies solely on questionnaires to assess consumers' brand loyalty towards Nestlé products despite the company offering a diverse range of products. Some respondents may not provide entirely honest and sincere responses, thereby limiting the study's ability to gain a deeper understanding of consumers' true intentions towards Nestlé products.

Moreover, the study examines only five variables, overlooking various other factors that could influence consumers' brand loyalty, such as distribution and advertising. Consequently, the study lacks comprehensive representation in understanding and describing the factors affecting consumers' brand loyalty to Nestlé products. Further constraints arise from the study's sample size, consisting of only 225 respondents, which, due to time and cost limitations, restricts the ability to analyze consumers' brand loyalty on a broader scale across India.

References

1. Aaker, D. (2003), "The power of the branded differentiator", MIT Sloan Management Review, Vol. 45 No. 1, pp. 83-7.
2. Aaker, D., & Keller, K. L. (1990). Consumer Evaluations of Brand Extensions. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(1), 27-41.
3. Abou-Shouk, M., & Soliman, M. (2021). The impact of gamification adoption intention on brand awareness and loyalty in tourism: The mediating Effect of customer engagement. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 20, 100559.
4. Ahmed, S., Al Asheq, A., Ahmed, E., Chowdhury, U. Y., Sufi, T., & Mostofa, M. G. (2022). The intricate relationships between consumers' loyalty and their perceptions of service quality, price, and satisfaction in restaurant service. *The TQM Journal*.
5. Al-Haddad, A. (2019). Social identification, brand image, and customer satisfaction as determinants of brand love. In *Creative business and social innovations for a sustainable future* (pp. 255-262). Springer, Cham.
6. Anam, J., Sanuri, B. M. M. S., & Ismail, B. L. O. (2018). Conceptualizing the relation between halal logo, perceived product quality, and the role of consumer knowledge. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*.
7. Annual Report "Nestlé S.A.", Vevey, Switzerland. 2014.
8. Bresciani, S., & Del Ponte, P. (2017). New brand logo design: customers' preference for brand name and icon. *Journal of Brand Management*, 24(5), 375-390.

9. Cadogan, J. W., & Foster, B. D. (2000). Relationship Selling and Customer Loyalty: An Empirical Investigation, *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 18(4), 185-199.
10. Cadogan, J. W., & Foster, B. D. (2000). Relationship Selling and Customer Loyalty: A Calder, B. J., Philips, L. W., & Tybout, A. M. (1981). Designing research for application. *The Journal of Consumer Research*, 8(2), 197-207.
11. Čater, B., & Čater, T. (2009). Relationship-value-based antecedents of customer satisfaction and loyalty in manufacturing. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*.
12. Chuenban, P., Sornsarut, P., & Pimdee, P. (2021). How brand attitude, brand quality, and brand value affect Thai canned tuna consumer brand loyalty. *Heliyon*, 7(2), e06301.
13. Clow, M. (2010). *Integrated Marketing Communications*. Pearson Education, Inc. publishing as Prentice Hall.
14. Company History – Nestle Industries Ltd. All about company history Retrieved from <https://www.nestle.in/aboutus/allaboutnestl%C3%A9> on 12/08/2021.
15. Corporate Watch, “Nestlé S.A.: Who, Where, How Much?” Vevey, Switzerland. 2012.
16. Cuong, D. T., & Khoi, B. H. (2021, January). Empirical Research on the Impact of Brand Awareness on Brand Loyalty: The Mediating Role of Brand Image. In *International Econometric Conference of Vietnam* (pp. 423-433). Springer, Cham.
17. Delgado-Ballester, E., & Munuera-Alemán, J. L. (2001). Brand trust in the context of consumer loyalty. *European Journal of Marketing*.
18. Dewi, L., & Putri, S. H. (2022). SERVICE QUALITY, CUSTOMER VALUE, AND PRICE TO CONSUMER SATISFACTION AT KOPI KENANGAN COFFEE SHOP. *International Journal of Social Science*, 1(6), 987-992.
19. Diputra, I. G. A. W., & Yasa, N. N. (2021). The influence of product quality, brand image, and brand trust on customer satisfaction and loyalty. *American International Journal of Business Management*, 4(1), 25-34.
20. Fathurahman, A. A., & Sihite, J. (2022). EFFECT OF PROMOTION, BRAND IMAGE, AND PRODUCT QUALITY ON REPURCHASE INTEREST THROUGH CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AS INTERVENING ON ERIGO APPAREL PRODUCTS. *Dinasti International Journal of Management Science*, 3(4), 621-631.
21. Frings, G. S. (2005). *Fashion: From Concept to Consumer* (8th Ed.). New Jersey: Pearson/Prentice Hall. Giunipero, L., & Daniel J. F. (2001). Purchasing practices in Saudi Arabia - an exploratory analysis. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 31, 686-704.
22. Frings, G. S. (2005). *Fashion: From Concept to Consumer* (8th Ed.). Pearson/Prentice Hall: New Jersey.
23. Hakim, L. N. (2021). Effect of Product Quality and Service Quality on Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as an Intervening Variables (Case Study on the Tirta Jasa Lampung Selatan Regional Company (PDAM)). *Economic Journal: Scientific Journal of Accountancy, Management and Finance*, 1(1), 48-56.
24. Hasan, T. (2008). Influence of Brand Name on Consumer Decision. *Umeå School of Business and Economics (USBE)*.
25. Hatta, I. H., Rachbini, W., & Parenrengi, S. (2018). Analysis of product innovation, product quality, promotion, price, and purchase decisions. *South East Asia Journal of Contemporary Business*, 16(5), 183-189.
26. Herrmann, A., Xia, L., Monroe, K. B., & Huber, F. (2007). The influence of price fairness on customer satisfaction: an empirical test in the context of automobile purchases. *Journal of product & brand management*.
27. Homburg, C., Schwemmler, M., & Kuehnl, C. (2015). New product design: Concept, measurement, and consequences. *Journal of Marketing*, 79(3), 41-56.
28. Japutra, A., Keni, K., & Nguyen, B. (2015). The impact of brand logo identification and brand logo benefit on Indonesian consumers' relationship quality. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*.
29. Jin, B., & Cho, H. J. (2018, June). The Differences between Internationalization of SMEs with Brand Names and those without Brand Names: An Abstract. In *Academy of Marketing Science World Marketing Congress* (pp. 665-666). Springer, Cham.
30. Keller, K. (2003). Brand Synthesis: The multidimensionality of Brand Knowledge. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 29(1).
31. Keller, K. L. (2003). *Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring and Managing Brand Equity*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
32. Keller, K. L. (2003). *Strategic brand management: building, measuring, and managing brand equity*. Prentice hall, upper saddle river, NEW Jersey.
33. Keller, K. L., Parameswaran, M. G., & Jacob, I. (2011). *Strategic brand management: Building, measuring, and managing brand equity*. Pearson Education India.
34. Klink, R. R., & Wu, L. (2017). Creating ethical brands: The role of brand name on consumer perceived ethicality. *Marketing Letters*, 28(3), 411-422.
35. Košičiarová, I., Nagyová, E., Holienčinová, M., & Rybanská, J. (2016). Quality Label as the Guarantee of Top Quality Agricultural and Food Products Produced in Slovak Republic - a Case Study of Slovak Food Market. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 64(6), 1937-1950.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.11118/actaun201664061937>

36. Kurniawan, M. A. (2022). The effects of perceived service quality, perceived benefits of booking apps, perceived sales promotion, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty as mediating roles towards customer repurchase intention of ride-hailing services in Jakarta (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Pelita Harapan).
37. Lau, M.-M., Chang, M.-T., Moon, K.-L., & Liu, W.-S. (2006). Brand loyalty in sportswear in Hong Kong. *Journal of textile and apparel, technology and management*, 5(1), 1-13.
38. Lim, M. K., Li, Y., & Song, X. (2021). Exploring customer satisfaction in cold chain logistics using a text mining approach. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.
39. Lin, Y., Liang, B., & Zhu, X. (2018). The Effect of Inventory Performance on Product Quality: The mediating Effect of Financial Performance. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*.
40. Lovelock, C. H. (2010). *Services Marketing*, (4th ed), New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
41. Mazhar, M., Daud, S., Arz Bhutto, S., & Mubeen, M. (2015). Impact of product packaging on consumers buying behavior: evidence from Karachi. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 16, 35-42.
42. Nestlé Group, "Quick Facts", Nestlé S.A., Vevey, Switzerland. 2013.
43. Oliver, R. L. (1997). *Satisfaction: A Behavioral Perspective on the Consumer*. New York: The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
44. P. Kotler and G. Armstrong, "Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran, Jilid 1," Jakarta: Erlangga, 2008.
45. Pathak, A., Calvert, G., & Velasco, C. (2017). Evaluating the impact of early-and late-acquired phonemes on the luxury appeal of brand names. *Journal of Brand Management*, 24(6), 522-545.
46. Perry, P., & Kyriakaki, M. (2014). The decision-making process of luxury fashion retail buyers in Greece. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*. Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 85-106.
47. Pihl, C. (2014). Brands, community, and style – exploring linking value in fashion blogging. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*. Vol. 18 No. 1, 2014 pp. 3- 19.
48. Prasetyo, B., Adil, M., Soelistya, D., & Rosyihuddin, M. (2022). The Importance of Product Quality, Price Perception and Service Quality in Achieving Customer Satisfaction. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(1).
49. PRASILOWATI, S. L., SUYANTO, S., SAFITRI, J., & WARDANI, M. K. (2021). The Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction: The Role of Price. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 8(1), 451-455.
50. Priambudi, R. R., Alvianna, S., Hermin, D., & Rachmadian, A. (2022). The Effect of Attractions, Facilities, and Prices on Customer Satisfaction at The Written Batik Celaket Center, Malang City. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 5(1), 91-97.
51. Raheem, A. R., Vishnu, P. A. R. M. A. R., & Ahmed, A. M. (2014). Impact of product packaging on consumer's buying behavior. *European journal of scientific research*, 122(2), 125–134.
52. Rehman, A., Zia-ur-rehman, M., & Akhtar, W. (2012). Factors affecting Brand Loyalty: A perspective of fast-food restaurants. *Actual Problems of Economics*, pp. 130, 13–20. Retrieved from <https://s3.amazonaws.com>
53. Rivai, J. (2021). The Role of Purchasing Decisions Mediating Product Quality, Price Perception, and Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction of Kopi Janji Jiwa. *Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 3(2), 31-42.
54. Rowley, J. (2005). The four Cs of customer loyalty. *Journal of Marketing Intelligence and Planning*. 23(6), 574-581.
55. Russell, R. S., & Taylor, B. W. (2006). *Operation Management: Quality and Competitiveness in a Global Environment* (5th Ed.). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: River Street.
56. Sääksjärvi, M., & Hellén K. (2013). How designers and marketers can work together to support consumers' happiness. *International Journal of Design* Vol. 7 No. 3. www.ijdesign.org.
57. Sanny, L., Marselli, D., Effandi, R., & Simek, L. (2021, August). The Impact of Instagram E-Marketing in SME Fashion Industry on Customer Satisfaction. In *2021 International Conference on Software Engineering & Computer Systems and 4th International Conference on Computational Science and Information Management (ICSECS-ICOCSIM)* (pp. 43-46). IEEE.
58. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). *Research for business—a skill-building approach*. John-Wiley and Sons, New York, NY, 4, 401-415.
59. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2011). *Business Research Methods: A skill-building approach*.
60. Souri, F. (2021). ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF BRAND IDENTITY ON BRAND PERFORMANCE, BRAND SATISFACTION AND BRAND LOVE IN IRAN. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government* Vol, 27(5).
61. Sudari, S., Tarofder, A., Khatibi, A., & Tham, J. (2019). Measuring the critical Effect of marketing mix on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction in food and beverage products. *Management Science Letters*, 9(9), 1385-1396.
62. Syafarudin, A. (2021). The Effect of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction Implications on Customer Loyalty in the Era of Covid-19. *Ilomata International Journal of Tax and Accounting*, 2(1), 71-83.
63. Tjahjono, E. J., Ellitan, L., & Handayani, Y. I. (2021). Product Quality and Brand Image Towards Customers' Satisfaction through Purchase Decision of Wardah Cosmetic Products in Surabaya. *Journal of Entrepreneurship & Business*, 2(1), 56-70.

64. Tsafarakis, S., Grigoroudis, E., & Matsatsinis, N. (2011). Consumer choice behaviour and new product development: an integrated market simulation approach. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 62, 1253–1267.
65. Uggla, H. (2001). emotional branding: how successful brands gain an irrational edge. *Organization of brand: Malmo Economic Travis Daryi*, p. 39.
66. W. J. Stanton and Y. Lamarto, “Prinsip Pemasaran Jilid 1,” Erlangga. Jakarta, 1993.
67. Waheed, S., Khan, M. M., & Ahmad, N. (2018). Product packaging and consumer purchase intentions. *Market Forces*, 13(2).
68. Wantara, P., & Tambrin, M. (2019). The Effect of price and product quality towards customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on Madura Batik. *International Tourism and Hospitality Journal*, 2(1), 1-9.
69. Wibowo, Y. G., Wulandari, R. H., & Qomariah, N. (2021). Impact of Price, Product Quality, and Promotion on Consumer Satisfaction in Cosmetics and Skincare. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 4(07), 978-986.
70. Wiharso, G., Prasetyo, J. H., Prakoso, B. S., & Fabrianto, L. (2022). The Effect Of Mobile Banking Product Quality On Customer Satisfaction Of Indonesian Sharia Bank Jakarta Wolter Monginsidi Branch. *Matriks: Jurnal Sosial dan Sains*, 3(2), 80-88.
71. Witek-Hajduk, M. K., & Grudecka, A. (2022). Does the developed-country brand name still matter? Consumers’ purchase intentions and ethnocentrism and materialism as moderators. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*.
72. Yoon, S. J., & Kim, J. H. (2000). An Empirical Validation of a Loyalty Model based on Expectation and Disconfirmation. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 17(2), 120-136.
73. Zhang, H., & Ma, Z. (2021). Is my design better? A co-creation perspective for online fashion design. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*.
74. Zhao, X., Wang, P., & Pal, R. (2021). The effects of agro-food supply chain integration on product quality and financial performance: Evidence from Chinese agro-food processing business. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 231, 107832.
75. Zia, A., Younus, S., & Mirza, F. (2021). Investigating the Impact of Brand Image and Brand Loyalty on Brand Equity: The Mediating Role of Brand Awareness. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(2), 1091-1106.